

Cult of Gauchito Gil

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A cult associated with the figure of legendary nineteenth-century outlaw Antonio "Gauchito" Gil gained prominence in Argentina in the 1990s. Antonio Gil was allegedly a gaucho (i.e., a skilled horseman and cattle tender) who robbed from the rich and helped the poor. He is venerated as a folk saint and is believed to possess great powers of intercession, especially over disreputable endeavours for which the help of official Catholic saints cannot be sought. His followers are typically working class, with a large presence among truck drivers. He is associated with the colour red and has a large number of dedicated roadside shrines on all of Argentina's major roads. Some Gauchito Gil shrines can also be found in neighbouring countries.

Date Range: 1990 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Argentina

Region tags: South America

Present-day Argentina

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Carballo, Cristina Teresa. "Paisajes del Gauchito Gil en Buenos Aires. ¿Neoculturas urbanas de fe?" *Espacio e Cultura* 43 (2018): 113-130.
- Source 2: Cerezo, Gastón. "Marcas religiosas, territorios y espacios en el culto al Gauchito Gil." In *Geografías de lo sagrado en la contemporaneidad*, ed. Cristina Teresa Carballo and Fabián Claudio Flores, 479-500. Bernal, Argentina: Universidad Nacional de Quilmes, 2019.
- Source 3: Graziano, Frank. "Gaucho Gil". In *Cultures of Devotion: Folk Saints of Spanish America*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2007.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.cultura.gob.ar/santos-populares-gauchito-gil-8664/>
- Source 1 Description: Article on the legend and cult of the Gauchito Gil on the website of the Ministry of Culture of Argentina.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.diversidadreligiosa.com.ar/blog/las-devociones-populares-en-la-literatura-3-el-santuario-del-gauchito-gil-en-mercedes-por-martin-caparrós/>
- Source 2 Description: Section dedicated to the cult of Gauchito Gil in the native city of the saint, Mercedes, from the book *El interior*, by journalist Martín Caparrós.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Gauchito Gil being a folk Catholic saint, his cult bears a direct link to official Catholicism. It also exhibits close links with the cults of other folk saints, in particular San La Muerte, to whom he was allegedly devoted, and Difunta Correa, whose cult, which also features roadside shrines, declined in popularity as the Gauchito's expanded. For more on San La Muerte and Difunta Correa, see the homonymous chapters in Graziano, *Cultures of Devotion* (2007: pp. 77-112 and 167-190).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: It depends. The cult overlaps with Catholicism and appropriates many of its symbols and practices, but it also includes a number of elements that clash with Catholic orthodoxy. Although many of Gauchito Gil's followers consider themselves Catholic, some see his cult as a popular alternative to a religion that is perceived as catering to the elites. At the same time, while some Catholic priests condemn the cult, others try to integrate it as a way of bringing the population closer to Catholicism (see M. Caparrós, *El interior*).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: It depends. The cult overlaps with Catholicism and appropriates many of its symbols and practices, but it also includes a number of elements that clash with Catholic orthodoxy. Although many of Gauchito Gil's followers consider themselves Catholic, some see his cult as a popular alternative to a religion that is perceived as catering to the elites. At the same time, while some Catholic priests condemn the cult, others try to integrate it as a way of bringing the population closer to Catholicism (see M. Caparrós, *El interior*).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 10000000

Notes: According to the 2019 National Survey on Religious Beliefs and Attitudes in Argentina ("Encuesta nacional sobre creencias y actitudes religiosas en Argentina") conducted by the National Scientific and Technological Research Council (CONICET), 23% of the total population of Argentina have at least a partial belief in Gauchito Gil.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 23

Notes: 23% of the total population of Argentina believe in Gauchito Gil, according to the 2019 National Survey on Religious Beliefs and Attitudes in Argentina ("Encuesta nacional sobre creencias y actitudes religiosas en Argentina") conducted by the National Scientific and Technological Research Council (CONICET).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 50000

Notes: Sanctuary of the city of Mercedes (Corrientes, Argentina). Overall size of the grounds: 5 hectares.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 9

Notes: As of 2023, the tallest monument is a 9 m statue built in Mercedes, the Gauchito's native city and the site of his largest shrine. Source: https://tn.com.ar/sociedad/el-gauchito-gil-mas-grande-de-la-argentina-en-corrientes-van-inaugurar-una-estatua-de-nueve-metros_929134/

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 1

Notes: The most common monuments are the small roadside shrines.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 1

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: With the exception of the supposed burial place of Antonio Gil, a pilgrimage site in the city of Mercedes.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Shrines built in public squares.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Statues

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: The iconography is mainly present in public spaces such as urban sanctuaries and roadside shrines. Many devotees have tattoos featuring Antonio Gil and iconographic elements such as boleadoras, the color red, or the cross in the back. Some devotees dress in full gaucho attire to attend festivities, sometimes the clothing is completely red. Iconographic elements, for example in holy cards representing the Gauchito, may be found in domestic altars.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: The cult of the Gauchito Gil is often associated with that of the grim reaper-style entity San La Muerte, of whom he is said to have been a devotee. Depictions of San La Muerte are frequent on shrines dedicated to the Gauchito.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The Gauchito is usually depicted in front of a Christian cross. See Graziano (2007, pp. 119-120): "The fusion of Gil and the cross then becomes visually explicit in the now standardized iconography. Gil stands in front of the cross—or, more accurately, is attached to it at his back—with his head proudly uplifted rather than bowed in agony like that of the crucified Christ. The overall impression is one of confidence and strength. This is more a resurrection than a crucifixion. Gil's right hand holds boleadoras (bolas), a symbol of gaucho culture. If earlier in this devotion the cross was prominent and the quasi-anonymous Gil—with an identity only as a victim—was secondary, now the cross is a backdrop that showcases the triumphant Gil in the foreground. Despite the implications of such iconography, devotees have little to say on the similarity of Gaucho Gil and Christ."

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Shrines often feature graphic representations of Gauchito Gil himself.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The colour red, boleadoras, trees or tree stumps. The colour red stands for the Federalist Party that Antonio Gil supposedly supported (see below); boleadoras (eng. "bolas") are a symbol of Gaucho culture (Graziano, 2007, p. 120); the trees represent the one from which Gil was hung. On the colour red, Graziano (2007, pp. 128-130) notes: "The color red has many meanings. For some devotees it represents blood and sacrifice, specifically Gil's spilled blood. Also suggestive, but not mentioned by devotees, are the broader uses of the color red for luck and protection. In Buenos Aires, for example,

many people put red ribbons on the rearview mirror of their car to protect them from envy. [...] More critical to Gaucho Gil devotion is the political affiliation designated by the color red. The color-coded struggle between the Federales (red) and the Unitarios (blue) during the nineteenth century was repeated in Corrientes Province by the corresponding parties, the Autonomistas (red) and the Liberales (blue). The Autonomistas were more traditional and associated with the lower classes, while the Liberales were more progressive and elitist. Because red is the color of Gaucho Gil devotion, many people presume that Gil belonged to the Autonomist party, which seems logical given his social class and rural values. [...] More likely, however, is that Gaucho Gil was among the troops of the Liberal party (blue). [...] Such recruitments tended to be forced, and Gil's desertion may have been partially inspired by his sympathies for the Autonomist cause. Thus Gil was blue by recruitment but had a red heart. In the end, the political content of the color red, which is also associated with revolution, might best represent Gaucho Gil not as a party affiliate but as a symbol of resistance"

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Roadside shrines, usually oriented towards the road.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Devotees adhere to usual Catholic beliefs concerning the afterlife. More idiosyncratic are their beliefs regarding the kind relationship that it is possible to establish with the miraculous dead.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Devotees of South American folk saints such as Gauchito Gil believe in the miraculous power of tragic death. The sites where such deaths took place (e.g., the sites of road accidents) are marked with crosses beside which passers-by begin to leave small offerings (candles, food, textiles, etc.). These sites are not necessarily graves, but, more frequently, the place where the tragedy occurred. The victims of such events are good candidates to become new folk saints. The objects are not interred and it is allowed for devotees to make use of them in case of need. On the power of tragic death in South American folk Catholicism, see Graziano, 2007, pp. 15-23.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Wealthier devotees or those asking for greater miracles sometimes leave valuable items as offerings (Graziano, 2007, p. 62).

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The funeral practices of devotees of South American folk saints are the same as those of other Catholics. Memorials marking the place where a death occurred, especially if the death was tragic, are of special relevance to South American folk religiosity.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Devotees of Gauchito Gil usually believe in the Catholic God. Although they acknowledge that the Gauchito is only an intermediary, in practice, the God who performs the miracles requested of the saint is an abstract figure that tends to fade into the background. Thanks for a fulfilled request are given to the Gauchito, not to God (Graziano, 2007, p. 12).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: While the Catholic God is not necessarily believed to have a specific connection to elites, the Catholic church is. Official saints, whose images often wear jewels and expensive clothing, are believed by devotees to be closer to elites and answer their prayers more, while folk saints answer to the lower classes.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Devotees are usually acquainted with Catholic doctrine, which does not allow worshipping of beings other than the high god. However, the abstract high god in the background is less important to them than the saint with whom they can communicate (Graziano, 2007, 12).

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: Only indirectly, through the saints.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Gauchito Gil is himself a previously human spirit.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: But this belief can be combined with those in other folk supernatural beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: However, folk saints are perceived as quasi-divine to their devotees.

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Gauchito Gil can take revenge against devotees who do not honour their oaths.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: As other folk saints, Gauchito Gil can take revenge on people who do not keep the promises made to him.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Done as a form of revenge against people who do not keep their promises.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Not as much as rewards. However, the idea that Gauchito can take revenge against those who fail to keep their promises is prevalent among his devotees. The type of punishment (sickness, economic drawbacks, disaster on journeys, etc) depends on the person and the nature of the promise that they did not keep.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Technically yes, but miracles are requested from and credited to Gauchito Gil.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Done by Gauchito Gil, in this particular case, or by other folk saints in which devotees may also believe.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Miracles are requested through offerings or sacrifices like going on pilgrimage. New offerings or sacrifices are offered once the petition is granted.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Highly emphasised.

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: But the view of many devotees, as well as some of the priests who fight against the cult, is that what makes it so attractive is that it is more tolerant and less restrictive than mainstream Catholicism (Graziano, 2007: 41).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: But Gauchito Gil tattoos are common among his followers.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings are left in exchange for miracles or simply to "build a relationship" with the saint. The value of an offering is relative to the economic situation of the offerer, some of whom are very poor.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Participation is not required, but is frequent. Rituals are more often performed in public spaces (in particular, at roadside shrines) than in private ones.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Participation is not required, but is frequent. The feast of Gauchito Gil is commemorated on January 8, supposedly the day of his execution. On that day, celebrations are held at various sanctuaries around the country. The main one, in the city of Mercedes, has been known to host up to 300,000 followers.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: Tattoos are not required, but frequent. Photo by hernantattoo - Own work, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, <https://www.zonatattoos.com/tattoo/96378>

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Not required, but the colour red is associated with Gauchito Gil, so followers often wear this colour in his sanctuaries.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: The colour red is associated with Gauchito Gil, so followers often wear ribbons, kerchiefs, hats, and other ornaments in that colour.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: Buses to the main sanctuary are provided by the group.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tourist companies also offer buses to pilgrimage sites.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Except for devotees who pursue a military career, but this choice would not be typically linked to their religious faith.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Most adherents are native Spanish speakers.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The calendar of Catholic saints.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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